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The irregularisation of migration and migrants' irregular condition: an assemblage perspective

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Abstract

This paper develops the concept of irregularity assemblage to account for the heterogeneous, dynamic, and relational processes through which migrant irregularity is produced, sustained, and contested across Europe. Drawing on insights from critical migration and border studies, assemblage theory, and feminist and postcolonial scholarship, we argue that irregularity is not a fixed legal category but an emergent condition generated through the intersection of multiple regulatory, material, and discursive regimes. Building on comparative evidence from six European countries (Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, and the United Kingdom) and at the EU level, the paper traces how immigration, labour, and welfare systems, together with local bureaucratic practices and public narratives, co-produce diverse configurations of irregularity. We show that these assemblages are historically and spatially contingent, shaped by crises and reforms—from the “hostile environment” in the UK to the “Cutro Decree” in Italy and the post-2015 securitisation of borders in the EU. The concept of irregularity assemblage foregrounds the relational entanglements between law, governance, and everyday life, illuminating how migrants and their families navigate, resist, and sometimes reproduce the very infrastructures that render them precarious. By re-centring irregularity as a process rather than a status, the paper contributes to a reconceptualisation of irregular migration beyond juridical or moral binaries, offering an analytical lens to examine how irregularity is made and unmade through the interplay of institutions, technologies, and lived experiences.

Keywords

Irregular migration, migration infrastructures, assemblage, hostile environment

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The irregularisation of migration and migrants' irregular condition: an assemblage perspective

Nando Sigona and Ilse van Liempt

Introduction

Irregular migration is one of the most politically charged and conceptually contested issues in global migration debates. While the phenomenon itself is not new, its framing as a crisis and as a challenge to sovereignty, security, and welfare has propelled it to the centre of policymaking and public discourse, particularly in Europe and North America. Irregular migration is inherently linked to geopolitics, migration politics and economic considerations in the light of globalization and capitalism (Cross 2013, Jansen et al. 2015, Jordan and Düvell 2002, Mainwaring 2019). Its political urgency has had a profound impact on scholarship, shaping research agendas, methods, and concepts. Academic work has often been required to engage with policy-driven problematisations of irregular migration—measuring numbers, estimating costs, designing enforcement strategies—while critical scholars have sought to deconstruct these framings, foregrounding the power relations that underpin them (Gonzales et 2019; van Liempt et al 2023).

More recently, the rise of irregular migration on the political agenda has been closely tied to its framing as a crisis. Media and policy discourses depict irregular migration as an exceptional and urgent threat requiring immediate intervention. In Europe, this crystallised during the so-called “migration crisis” of 2015-16 (Crawley et al 2018, Sigona 2018, Siegel & Nagy 2018, Mainwaring 2019), but the language of crisis has long permeated debates, from the Mediterranean to the US–Mexico border. Such crisis talks (DeBono 2016) that frame and reproduce ‘crises’ as exceptionalized and highly politicized moments naturalise restrictive measures, justify the expansion of enforcement

Academic research has inevitably been influenced by this sense of urgency. Governments, international organisations, and NGOs have funded projects to count irregular migrants, estimate fiscal impacts, or evaluate enforcement. The result has been a proliferation of policy-oriented knowledge that often mirrors official categories and priorities. Yet critical scholarship has consistently pushed back, arguing that crisis framings obscure the structural and historical roots of irregular migration and delegitimise migrant claims to rights and belonging.

One of the most visible arenas in which these struggles play out is terminology. The words used to describe irregular migrants are never neutral but carry distinct political and analytical weight. In political and media parlance, “illegal immigrant” remains widespread, emphasising law-breaking and criminality. Civil society actors in the US popularised “undocumented migrant” to highlight the absence of authorisation rather than inherent illegality, framing migrants as rights-bearing individuals rather than criminals. In Europe, “irregular migrant” has become the preferred term in academic and policy circles, promoted by institutions such as the European Union and the International Organization for Migration (IOM 2011) as a more neutral descriptor. The French *sans papiers* movement recast the debate by rejecting state labels altogether and asserting migrants’ political agency through the language of rights.

Scholars have highlighted the power/knowledge dynamics at stake in these terms. Kubal (2013) proposed the concept of semi-legality to capture statuses that do not fit neatly into legal/illegal binaries, illustrating how the instability of legal status is itself a product of law. Merolla et al (2013) showed that terminology alone may not radically alter public attitudes, but broader issue frames strongly influence perceptions of migration. The definitional debate, then, is not simply semantic but

constitutive: terms do not merely describe reality but shape it, influencing how migrants are governed, how they are perceived, and how they perceive themselves.

This contestation reflects broader configurations of power and knowledge. Official categories serve administrative purposes, but they also legitimise certain policy responses and marginalise others. Academic categories can either reinforce or destabilise these framings. Social movements mobilise language strategically to shift narratives and claim rights. The growing scholarly attention to terminology signals recognition that the act of naming irregularity is itself a political practice, deeply implicated in the struggles over migration governance.

The political urgency surrounding irregular migration has shaped not only terminology but also the broader production of knowledge. Much early research was responsive to policy imperatives, producing statistics, forecasts, and evaluations of enforcement. This strand of scholarship contributed to public debates but often reproduced the state's categories and problem frames. By contrast, critical approaches sought to destabilise these framings by emphasising processes of irregularisation rather than static conditions.

This critical turn emphasised that irregular migrants are not simply people lacking documents but subjects whose status is actively produced through restrictive laws, bureaucratic practices, and everyday enforcement. De Genova (2002) argued that “illegality” is central to the governance of migration, not a peripheral by-product. Coutin (2000) illustrated how bureaucracies continually shift migrants' status, producing instability and vulnerability. Later ethnographies highlighted the lived dimensions of irregularity: uncertainty, waiting, exclusion, but also agency and resistance (Sigona 2012; Griffiths 2014).

The urgency of irregular migration as a political problem has thus created a dual dynamic in scholarship. On one hand, research has had to respond to immediate political demands for knowledge. On the other, it has sought to develop critical perspectives that resist and deconstruct policy framings. This tension has given the field both its richness and its fragmentation.

A recurring theme in critical research is the rejection of binary thinking about legality and illegality. While official discourse often presents migration in stark categories, scholars have shown that legal status is fluid, shifting over time and across contexts. Menjívar (2006) described “liminal legality” to capture conditional or temporary authorisations that leave migrants vulnerable. Kubal's (2013) “semi-legality” underscores how migrants may occupy ambiguous statuses, simultaneously recognised and excluded. The notion of “irregularisation”, we argue in this paper, further extends this, emphasising that migrants may move in and out of status across their life course, and that the potential to fall into irregularity is increasingly a defining feature by design of contemporary migration regimes.

This perspective highlights the shifting boundaries of regularity. Policies such as Brexit in the UK or the tightening of visa regimes in Europe demonstrate how people can move from regular to irregular status not because of personal decisions but because of broader political transformations (Benson and Sigona 2024). At the same time, regularisation schemes and temporary protections can partially reverse this, though often without providing long-term stability. The result is a landscape of precarious legal statuses in which irregularity is not an exception but part of the continuum of migration governance.

The combination of political urgency, terminological contestation, and fragmented disciplinary approaches has generated a large but uneven field of scholarship. Certain areas—such as the structural determinants of irregular migration, the lived experience of undocumented migrants, and the nexus between labour and immigration status precarity—are well developed. Others, such as the

intersection of irregularity with narratives and perceptions, or the experiences of irregular migrants in the Global South, remain underexplored.

The challenge now is to move beyond fragmented literatures and to conceptualise irregularity in ways that capture its multiple dimensions and their interaction. This paper proposes to do so through the lens of assemblage theory (DeLanda 2016, Deleuze and Guattari 1987), which foregrounds the relational, dynamic, and multi-scalar character of social phenomena. Assemblage thinking allows us to conceptualise irregularity not as a fixed condition but as an emergent constellation of regulatory frameworks, discourses, perceptions, and lived experiences which offer unique insights into the situated experiences of irregularity for migrants, what we call the irregular condition.

The following section provides an overview of scholarly literature on irregular migration, tracing how scholarship has developed across disciplines and regions, and identifying the hot spots and blind spots that shape the current research landscape.

State of the Art of Irregular Migration

Irregular migration has emerged as one of the most dynamic and politically salient areas of migration research. From its origins in structural analyses of Mexican–US migration (Massey and Espinosa 1997; Massey et al 2002) to contemporary studies of everyday life, political economy, and comparative governance, the field has undergone a major transformation. This section reviews the literature, identifying key contributions, geographical emphases, and areas of neglect.

From structural determinants to the social production of illegality

The earliest systematic scholarship on irregular migration emerged in North America in the 1970s and 1980s, focusing on migration from Mexico to the United States. These studies identified structural determinants as central drivers: migrant-receiving countries benefitted from cheap and flexible labour, while sending states benefitted from remittances and the partial alleviation of unemployment and inequality. Portes (1978: 477) emphasised the role of economic demand in the United States alongside the pressures of underdevelopment in Mexico, while Portes and Bach (1985) examined Cuban and Mexican migration to highlight the intersection of labour markets and political regimes.

A central finding of this early body of work was the paradoxical effect of immigration control. Restrictive enforcement did not necessarily reduce inflows but instead contributed to enforced immobility, as migrants who might otherwise circulate became “trapped” in the United States. Massey and Espinosa (1997) demonstrated this through survey evidence, while Cornelius (2001) and Massey et al. (2002) showed that border militarisation increased costs and risks, encouraging settlement rather than return. These findings challenged the assumption that tighter borders would reduce irregular migration, revealing instead the adaptive strategies of migrants and the unintended consequences of enforcement. Sassen (1996) situated irregular migration within global restructuring, arguing that restrictive immigration regimes coexisted with economic transformations that generated persistent demand for migrant labour. Together, these contributions established irregular migration as a structural feature of global capitalism, not a side effect or anomaly.

As the field expanded, researchers recognised the diversity of irregular migrants and their multiple routes into irregularity. Migration without papers was often a rite of passage or socially embedded practice sustained by social networks (Chavez 1992; Hagan 2008; Koser & Pinkerton 2002; Bloch et al 2014). This broadened the analysis from structural causes to social, cultural, and familial dynamics.

Yet, the field also became fragmented across disciplines, with sociologists, anthropologists, political scientists, and legal scholars often working in parallel. Blind spots persisted: while research on children, unaccompanied minors, and the 1.5 and second generations grew, there was relatively little attention to the specific experiences of young adults as undocumented migrants, despite the centrality of legal status in transitions to adulthood.

The late 1990s and 2000s witnessed a decisive theoretical turn with the concept of the social production of illegality. De Genova (2002) argued that “illegality” is not a natural state but actively produced by law and enforcement, rendering migrants deportable and therefore governable. Coutin (2000) described how Salvadorans were “illegalised” through bureaucratic practices, while Ngai (2004) traced the historical construction of the “illegal alien” in US immigration law. Menjivar’s (2006) concept of liminal legality and Kubal’s (2013) notion of semi-legality extended this framework, capturing in-between statuses that defy binary classifications. This body of work marked a fundamental shift: irregularity was no longer seen as an individual deficit but as a relational and political process.

Lived irregularity: everyday life, temporality, and bordering

Building on this conceptual shift, ethnographic research explored how irregularity is experienced in everyday life. Sigona (2012; Bloch et al 2014) analysed how legal status permeates social networks, trust, and belonging among irregular migrants in the UK. Willen (2007) developed a critical phenomenology of “illegality” among migrant workers in Tel Aviv, examining embodied effects of abjection and criminalisation. Gonzales (2011) described how undocumented youth in the US face the painful transition into “illegality” as adulthood closes off opportunities for education and employment, and Dreby (2015) describes how policies undermine immigrant families.

The temporal dimensions of irregularity have attracted particular attention. Griffiths (2014) described the uncertain and suspended lives of refused asylum seekers and detainees in the UK, while Schuster (2011) explored how waiting defines the asylum process. Jacobsen et al. (2021) highlight how waiting is configured in specific legal, material, and socio-cultural situations, as well as how migrants encounter, incorporate, and resist temporal structures. Andersson (2014) analysed deportation regimes in southern Europe, showing how cycles of anticipation, capture, and return structure migrants’ futures. These accounts emphasise irregularity as a temporal condition, defined as much by waiting and uncertainty as by exclusion.

Research on everyday bordering has further illuminated how enforcement extends into daily life (Yuval-Davis et al. 2018; Griffiths and Yeo 2021). The UK’s “hostile environment” policies embed immigration checks into housing, employment, healthcare, and education, multiplying the sites of potential irregularisation. This extension of control transforms irregularity into an omnipresent condition, shaping even mundane encounters.

Feminist and intersectional scholarship has underscored how irregularity is differentiated by gender, race, and age (Özdemir 2023). Sigona and Hughes (2012) highlighted how undocumented children experience exclusion in education and services, while Dreby (2012) analysed the burden of deportation on Mexican families. Anderson (2000) and Parreñas (2001) showed how migrant women in domestic and care work face compounded vulnerabilities, dependent on employers for both livelihood and status. These insights remind us that irregularity is not experienced uniformly but is profoundly shaped by social hierarchies.

Labour markets, political economy, and irregular incorporation

A parallel body of literature has examined how irregularity shapes migrants' incorporation into labour markets. Goldring and Landolt (2011) theorised the work–citizenship matrix, showing how insecure legal status and precarious employment reinforce each other, producing long-term consequences for mobility and belonging. In Southern Europe, researchers highlighted the structural reliance on irregular migrant labour. Calavita (2007) described how Spain's economy depended on irregular migrants who remained legally marginalised, encapsulated in the paradox of being “wanted but not welcome.” Ambrosini (2013) identified a similar “pragmatic tolerance” in Italy, where irregular migrants sustain care and construction sectors but are denied secure rights. Following this line, states have an interest in maintaining irregularity. Some authors even underline that these exploitable labour populations are deliberately kept mobile to enhance the “flexibility” of this labour force (e.g. Tazzioli 2020)

These insights connect to broader analyses of the political economy of irregularity. Castles (2010) argued that irregular migration reflects global social transformations, while Sassen (2006) showed how global economic restructuring sustains demand for precarious labour. Cities in particular have become highly dependent on irregular labour in a neo-liberal context where outsourcing public services to private businesses as well as cuts in benefits have resulted in the rise of a parallel economy that highly depends on irregular immigrant labour, like domestic workers (Anderson 2000, Bloch and Chimienti 2011), but also care and sex workers (Garofalo Geymonat et al. 2023). Within this context of employment, irregular migrants often fall within “the double” irregularity, being undeclared towards authorities both as workers and as migrants. Rumsby (2024) has proposed an everyday political economy, emphasising how structural conditions intersect with household strategies of debt, remittances, and survival.

The gendered and racialised dimensions of this political economy are clear. Anderson (2000) and Parreñas (2001) demonstrated how domestic and care sectors exploit women's irregularity. Ambrosini (2013) highlighted women's concentration in informal care work in Italy, while Bloch, Sigona and Zetter (2011) showed how racialised minorities in the UK are disproportionately targeted by enforcement and confined to precarious labour. More recently, Benson and Sigona (2025) analysed how East Europeans were racialised post-Brexit. Together, these studies confirm that irregularity is not an incidental status but a structural feature of labour markets, differentiated by gender and race.

Comparative configurations and political/legal cultures

Comparative research has revealed how irregularity takes distinct configurations depending on legal and political cultures. Sciortino and Cvajner (2010) argued that irregularity arises from mismatches between subsystems—law, economy, politics, and welfare—producing stratified statuses. In Southern Europe, restrictive laws combined with labour demand have generated large irregular populations managed through periodic regularisations. In Northern Europe, tighter controls and limited regularisation pathways have produced smaller but more entrenched irregular groups.

In the UK, Sigona and Hughes (2012) described a “policy impasse,” where migrants are trapped in limbo due to restrictive laws and limited exit routes. Spencer and Triandafyllidou (2020) provided a Europe-wide synthesis, highlighting both shared dynamics and national variation.

Geographically, the literature remains uneven. In the United States, research has emphasised deportability, liminal legality, and the lives of undocumented youth (De Genova 2002; Menjivar 2006; Gonzales 2011). In Europe, scholarship has focused on bordering, regularisation, and welfare regimes (Calavita 2007; Ambrosini 2013; Spencer & Triandafyllidou 2020). Beyond these regions, studies are

limited. Willen (2007) examined irregularity in Israel, while Reeves (2013) and Urinboyev (2020) analysed migrants navigating hybrid regimes in the former Soviet region. With some significant exceptions, despite significant irregular migration in South Africa, the Gulf States, and Latin America, these contexts remain underexplored, a notable blind spot given the globalisation of irregular migration governance, but also revealing of different situated framings of mobility.

Taken together, the scholarship on irregular migration has developed from structural analyses of cross-border labour flows into a multidimensional field concerned with legal production, everyday life, political economy, and comparative governance. Early work revealed the structural determinants of irregularity and the paradoxical consequences of enforcement. Later scholarship emphasised the social production of illegality, while ethnographies brought attention to the lived experience of uncertainty, temporality, and exclusion. Political economy analyses underscored how irregularity sustains key labour markets, while comparative studies revealed its differentiated configurations across legal and political cultures. Feminist and intersectional contributions have cut across these strands, reminding us that irregularity is lived differently depending on gender, race, and age.

Geographically, research has been concentrated in the US and Europe, with limited sustained analysis of the Global South, even as irregular migration governance has become increasingly globalised through EU externalisation and the UN's Global Compact. Longitudinal studies tracing migrants' trajectories of irregularisation remain scarce, leaving important questions about temporality and change unanswered.

The literature highlights irregularity as a dynamic, relational, and multidimensional condition, but one that has often been studied in silos. These limitations point to the need for an integrative framework capable of holding together the legal, economic, social, and discursive dimensions of irregularity. In the following section, we argue that an assemblage approach provides such a framework, enabling us to conceptualise irregularity not as a static status but as an unstable constellation of practices, regulations, perceptions, and lived experiences.

Assemblage in the Social Sciences and Migration Studies

Assemblage theory has become an increasingly influential framework across the social sciences, offering a way of thinking that moves beyond linear causality and fixed categories to emphasise the contingent, relational, and multi-scalar nature of social phenomena. It allows us to see the world not as composed of discrete, stable entities but as emergent constellations of heterogeneous elements—human and non-human, material and discursive, institutional and affective—that temporarily co-function to produce particular configurations.

Foundations, applications, and critiques

The concept of assemblage was most fully articulated in Gilles Deleuze and Félix Guattari's *A Thousand Plateaus* (1987), part of their *Capitalism and Schizophrenia* project. For them, assemblages (*agencements*) are "multiplicities" formed by relations among heterogeneous components. Crucially, they are defined not by essence but by connections. An assemblage, as Deleuze and Parnet (2002: 69) put it, is "a multiplicity which is made up of many heterogeneous terms and which establishes liaisons, relations between them, across ages, sexes and reigns – different natures. Thus, the assemblage's only unity is that of a co-functioning: it is a symbiosis, a 'sympathy'." The English "assemblage" translates the French *agencement*, which highlights not only the resulting arrangement but also the dynamic act of putting together. Assemblages are thus always provisional, contingent, and in flux. Manuel DeLanda

(2016) systematised these insights into a comprehensive exposition of assemblage theory. He clarified its conceptual architecture—distinguishing between material and expressive components, relations of exteriority, and emergent properties—and demonstrated its application across sociology, linguistics, military studies, and beyond. DeLanda’s work made assemblage thinking accessible to social scientists, while emphasising its relational ontology: the idea that entities derive their properties from interactions rather than from intrinsic essences.

The term ‘assemblage’ is increasingly used in a wide range of scholarship and has become a familiar part of the lexicon of contemporary social-spatial theory (Anderson and McFarlane, 2011). Jane Bennett (2010) mobilised the term to highlight the agency of non-human matter—food, metals, storms—as co-actors in political and social processes. Anna Tsing (2015) deployed assemblage to capture how precarious livelihoods and capitalist ruination generate emergent, unpredictable forms of collaboration and survival. More recently, Lewis and Spratt (2024) applied assemblage to comparative education policy, showing how policies are shaped by mobilities and connections across contexts, challenging linear models of policy transfer.

In the broader social sciences, assemblage has been especially influential in studies of governance and urbanism. Ong and Collier (2005) argued that globalisation is best understood as a proliferation of assemblages—configurations of technologies, policies, and discourses that travel, adapt, and recombine across contexts. Ong (2006) used assemblage to conceptualise graduated sovereignty, showing how states govern different populations through uneven combinations of market logics, humanitarian interventions, and biopolitical techniques. In urban studies, McFarlane (2011) employed assemblage to analyse cities as dynamic entanglements of infrastructures, practices, and discourses, challenging static or totalising models of urban order. Van Liempt (2015) used assemblage thinking to study emerging surveillance ‘assemblages’ in urban nightlife districts. She shows how human as well as non-human elements are assembled in specific ways in various spatial and temporal settings and collaborations between the actors may only be contingently obligatory resulting in internal tensions about the discourses and practices of surveillance at night. At the same time, assemblage thinking has faced criticism. Brenner et al. (2011) caution against its analytical looseness and tendency toward descriptive empiricism, where everything becomes an assemblage and explanatory force is diluted. These critiques underscore the importance of using assemblage not as a totalising ontology but as a heuristic device—a way to foreground multiplicity, relationality, and contingency without assuming that assemblage itself explains everything.

Assemblage in migration studies

Migration research has increasingly drawn on assemblage thinking to move beyond state-centred and linear models of governance. In *Territory, Authority, Rights*, Sassen (2006) applied assemblage to show how global arrangements of power and membership emerge from contingent intersections of legal frameworks, markets, and rights discourses. Salter (2013) extended this to the global mobility regime, conceptualising it as an assemblage that manages circulation not only through exclusion and surveillance but also through inclusion, facilitation, and acceleration.

Assemblage has also been used to interrogate the subjective dimensions of migration. Özlem Ögtem-Young’s *The Shape of Belonging* (2023) reconceptualises belonging as a dynamic, multi-dimensional, and often paradoxical process. Based on interviews with unaccompanied young people in the UK, Ögtem-Young develops an account of belonging that incorporates affective, emotional, political, symbolic, virtual, and actual dimensions, while also recognising its ruptures and contradictions. In

doing so, she challenges static, exclusionary notions of belonging and demonstrates how assemblage exposes the tensions and paradoxes of migrants' lives under conditions of precarity and control.

Ögtem-Young (2023) also extends assemblage into the methodological domain by conceptualising the research process itself as a “research assemblage”. Drawing on Fox and Alldred (2015; 2017), she describes research as a multiplicity of relations and events involving not only participants but also tools, technologies, frameworks, and researchers themselves. From this perspective, research is not a neutral mirror of reality but an event producing knowledge through what Barad (2007) calls intra-actions—the entanglement of theories, methods, tools, subjectivities, and affectivities. While detailed, the crucial insight is that assemblage invites reflexivity about how knowledge production is itself contingent, situated, and relational.

Assemblage and the ‘irregular condition’

Assemblage approaches are especially productive in the study of irregular migration. As Section 2 showed, the literature has highlighted the legal production of illegality, the phenomenology of lived irregularity, the political economy of precarious labour, and the politics of terminology and perception. Yet these strands have often remained siloed. Assemblage offers a way to integrate them, tracing how irregularity is assembled across infrastructures, regulatory frameworks, discourses, technologies, and migrant strategies.

This was the motivation behind Gonzales et al. (2019) introduction of the “illegality assemblage.” This concept foregrounded the relational and processual dimensions of illegality, showing how it emerges from multiple sites and actors rather than from law alone. Building on this, Sigona et al. (2021) linked the illegality assemblage to debates on migration infrastructures. Their work demonstrated how irregularity is shaped not only by rules and enforcement but also by infrastructures of mobility, communication, finance, and brokerage that mediate opportunities for movement and settlement (see also Xiang & Lindquist 2014). For Sigona et al. (2021), infrastructures constitute crucial yet often overlooked arenas where irregularity is assembled, mediated and contested.

Seen through this lens, irregular migration is not a fixed condition but a dynamic and contingent assemblage. Visa policy may reshape labour demand; public narratives may influence enforcement priorities; migrants' mobility practices may reconfigure governance. Assemblage draws attention to these processes of co-functioning, emphasising multiplicity rather than unity.

Using assemblage in this way helps address persistent challenges in the field. It bridges macro-level political economy with micro-level ethnography, showing how global inequalities and state practices are lived through everyday uncertainty and temporality. It accommodates national variation while also capturing transnational flows of technologies, practices, and discourses. It integrates legal, social, and affective dimensions, acknowledging irregularity as simultaneously structural and lived.

Crucially, we use assemblage heuristically rather than ontologically. Assemblage is not a total theory of society but a conceptual lens that foregrounds relationality, contingency, and dynamism. It enables us to move beyond binaries of legality and illegality, structure and agency, state and migrant, to grasp irregularity as an emergent and unstable constellation. In this way, assemblage provides a generative framework for advancing the study of irregular migration, opening new possibilities for dialogue across disciplines and methods.

In the following section, we develop this framework further by identifying three key dimensions of the irregularity assemblage: regulatory frameworks and practices; narratives and perceptions; and gendered and racialised experiences.

Assemblages of irregularity in Europe

Building on the conceptual discussion in Section 3, this section examines how irregularity is assembled in practice. Rather than treating irregularity as a fixed legal status or a homogeneous migrant condition, we foreground its emergence at the intersection of diverse and contingent elements: legal and policy frameworks, bureaucratic practices, political agendas, labour market regimes, discursive constructions, and lived experiences. Assemblage thinking directs attention to how these heterogeneous elements co-function, producing irregularity not as a stable category but as a dynamic and contested condition.

The analysis is informed by the findings of the Horizon Europe and UKRI-funded “Improving the living and working conditions of irregularised migrant families in Europe (I-CLAIM)” project. I-CLAIM provides a unique vantage point for developing this approach. By combining comparative analysis of legal and policy infrastructures, in-depth studies of narratives and perceptions, and ethnographic research on migrant lives and work, I-CLAIM illustrates how irregularity is made and remade across multiple domains and scales, revealing different but interconnected dimensions of the irregularity assemblage.

In what follows, we organise the analysis into three dimensions. Firstly, we explore the infrastructures of irregularity and analyse how national and EU-level governance assemble irregularity through visa regimes, legal categories, bureaucratic practices, and enforcement mechanisms. Secondly, we turn to narratives and perceptions, showing how political discourse, media framings, and public attitudes constitute an essential layer of the irregularity assemblage. Finally, we focus on the lived experiences of migrants with precarious legal status in agriculture, food delivery, and domestic work, illustrating how irregularity is refracted through gendered, racialised, and classed relations in everyday life.

Regulatory Frameworks as Infrastructures

The infrastructures of irregularity in Europe are neither accidental nor uniform. They are the outcome of intersecting legal frameworks, bureaucratic practices, political agendas, and labour market regimes, assembled across scales of governance. Irregularity emerges not from a single law or policy but from the dynamic interplay of elements that, together, produce migrants’ precarious and conditional statuses. A comparative analysis of six European countries (Italy, Poland, Germany, the UK, the Netherlands, Finland) shows that despite national variation, common logics underpin these infrastructures (Näre et al., 2024). These logics—temporary and conditional admission schemes, reliance on liminal statuses, and the outsourcing of enforcement—demonstrate that irregularity is a governed condition rather than a policy failure. The European Commission adds another layer, coordinating and amplifying irregularisation through its directives, funding mechanisms, and political priorities (Carrera & Colombi, 2025).

Temporary and conditional migration schemes

Across Europe, temporary and conditional migration programmes are central to how irregularity is assembled. These schemes facilitate access to labour markets but deliberately restrict permanence, producing migrants who are both needed and disposable.

Italy's reliance on seasonal permits and periodic *sanatorie* (regularisations) epitomises this dynamic (Palumbo & Marchetti, 2024). Migrants are brought in to meet labour demand in agriculture or care but denied stable residence; periodic amnesties offer temporary relief without altering the underlying precarity. Poland presents a similar pattern: simplified visa procedures for Ukrainians, and, up to 2022, Russians and Belarusians enable mass inflows, but permits are short-term and dependent on employers (Matuszczyk et al. 2024). When contracts end or paperwork is delayed, migrants quickly fall into irregularity.

This logic is not confined to Southern and Eastern Europe. In the UK, the post-Brexit migration regime has deepened reliance on employer-sponsored visas, particularly in sectors like care, hospitality, and agriculture (Piemontese & Sigona, 2024). Sponsorship ties migrants' legality to their employers, creating a structural risk of irregularisation if employment ends. In Finland, residence permits are often conditional on meeting stringent documentation or income thresholds; failure to comply results in the rapid loss of status (Merikoski et al 2024).

These cases show that sponsorship and conditionality are widespread features of European migration governance. Irregularity is not simply the absence of legality but a predictable outcome of schemes designed to ensure flexibility for states and employers while keeping migrants' futures uncertain.

Liminal statuses and protracted uncertainty

A second recurring feature is the proliferation of liminal legal categories that blur the line between legality and illegality. These statuses neither grant secure residence nor enforce deportation, leaving migrants in prolonged uncertainty.

Germany's *Duldung* (tolerated status) is the most cited example: migrants are formally recognised but excluded from secure residence and full rights (Rheindorf et al 2024). Yet similar conditions exist elsewhere. In the UK, large numbers of people live with precarious statuses such as "appeal rights exhausted," unable to regularise but not removed (Piemontese & Sigona, 2024). In Italy, refused asylum seekers often remain in the country without secure status, tolerated in practice but excluded from rights (Palumbo & Marchetti, 2024). In Finland, restrictive post-2015 asylum reforms created a population of migrants stuck "pending removal," living for years in legal limbo (Merikoski et al 2024).

These liminal categories illustrate the assemblage of irregularity: bureaucratic discretion, legal contestation, and enforcement constraints co-function to produce migrants who are simultaneously present and excluded. They are tolerated as workers or neighbours but denied membership and security. Crucially, these statuses reveal that irregularity is not a binary but a spectrum, managed through the deliberate creation of "in-between" positions.

Outsourced enforcement and local tensions

A third dynamic is the outsourcing of enforcement, which extends immigration control into the infrastructures of everyday life. The UK's "hostile environment" is the clearest example, embedding immigration checks into housing, employment, banking, and healthcare (Piemontese & Sigona, 2024). Teachers, doctors, and landlords are conscripted as border agents, diffusing immigration control across society and effectively irregularising migrants beyond their legal status.

Other countries rely on similar logics. In Germany, local bureaucrats exercise wide discretion in issuing or withdrawing tolerated status (Rheindorf et al 2024). In the Netherlands, national authorities restrict access to welfare and housing for irregular migrants, but municipalities and NGOs often step in to provide support, creating tensions between national exclusion and local accommodation (Hajer et al 2024).

These examples show how irregularity is produced not only through national laws but also through delegated enforcement and local practices. The assemblage perspective highlights how infrastructures of irregularity emerge from the interactions of diverse actors—states, municipalities, employers, NGOs—whose agendas and practices sometimes align, sometimes clash.

EU-level governance: coordination and amplification

Beyond national contexts, irregularity is also assembled at the supranational level. Carrera and Colombi (2025) show how the European Commission operates as a complex assemblage of directorates, mandates, and agendas. Different DGs (e.g. HOME, JUST, EMPLOY) pursue competing priorities—border control, rights protection, labour mobility—but their interaction often produces contradictions. Irregularity emerges from the tensions between these logics as much as from coherent policy design.

Externally, the Commission shapes member states' infrastructures of irregularity through directives, communications, and funding instruments. By prioritising return, border management, and deterrence, while leaving regularisation and inclusion largely to national discretion, the Commission creates an EU-wide enforcement architecture without corresponding mechanisms of security. This asymmetry amplifies irregularity across member states.

Crucially, viewing the Commission through an assemblage lens also reveals openings for contestation. Commission officials, member state representatives, municipalities, NGOs, and trade unions interact in ways that can generate contingent alliances around issues such as labour rights or humanitarian protection. Recognising the multiplicity of actors and agendas enables a more nuanced understanding of how irregularity is both entrenched and contested within EU governance.

The infrastructures of irregularity in Europe share common logics: temporary and conditional migration schemes, liminal statuses that institutionalise uncertainty, and the outsourcing of enforcement into everyday life. These dynamics, while configured differently across national contexts, demonstrate that precarisation and conditionality are features by design of migration governance. Irregularity is not a residual anomaly but a systemic outcome.

The EU level adds a further layer, coordinating and amplifying irregularisation while also generating contradictions that can open space for intervention. Assemblage thinking helps us to trace these dynamics across scales, showing how irregularity is continually assembled by diverse actors and practices. At the same time, it draws attention to the potential for contingent alliances—between municipalities, NGOs, unions, and even EU officials—that might reconfigure infrastructures toward more inclusive outcomes.

By situating infrastructures within the irregularity assemblage, we see irregularity as a dynamic, multi-scalar condition: produced through governance logics of precarisation, sustained by labour market demand, contested through local and supranational practices. This systemic but unstable character sets the stage for the next dimensions of analysis—narratives and perceptions (Section 4.2) and lived experiences (Section 4.3)—which together reveal how irregularity is constituted discursively and experientially as well as institutionally.

Narratives and perceptions of irregularity

Narratives and perceptions constitute a crucial dimension of the irregularity assemblage. They do not merely reflect an external reality of irregular migration but actively contribute to its constitution by framing what irregularity is, who counts as “irregular,” and what responses are deemed legitimate.

Irregular migration attracts disproportionate media attention and the media coverage tends to represent irregular migration as an unambiguous and uncontested concept and a clear and fixed legal category. It appears logically straightforward that we should be able to tell whether a person is irregular or not. In reality, it is much more complex, and historically the lines of irregularity are highly dynamic as the priorities of migration regimes are likely to shift over time (from outward to inward migration, from asylum to labour migration). Some categories of irregular migrants are hyper-visible in media or policy debates (e.g., young males arriving by boat), whereas other types of irregular migration hardly get any attention (e.g., privileged visa overstayers). It is telling in this regard how underaged migrants are highly visible in discussions on irregular migration in the United States, while they are rather underrepresented in similar discussions in Europe (Derluyn and Broekaert 2008, Lems et al. 2020).

Narratives produced in political arenas, media, and civil society, and perceptions circulating among the public, intersect with regulatory infrastructures and labour regimes to legitimise precarisation and conditionality of status. They also shape how migrants experience their lives and how they are received by employers, landlords, neighbours, and co-workers. This section draws on I-CLAIM's WP4 reports on political and media discourses and on survey-based analyses of public perceptions to illustrate how irregularity is discursively assembled across Europe.

Narratives across Europe

The discursive construction of irregularity across European countries reveals striking commonalities as well as national variations. A central theme across contexts is the predominance of border and asylum narratives. Migrants without secure status are most often portrayed as clandestine border-crossers or failed asylum seekers. In Germany, Rheindorf and Vollmer (2025) show how asylum-related narratives dominate public and political discourse, framing irregularity as a problem of failed asylum claims and deportations. In Poland, Grzymała-Kazłowska and Homel-Ficenes (2025) identify similar tendencies, with narratives focusing on attempts at irregular entry through border crossings and overstaying of student or work visas, situating irregularity firmly within state-centric notions of territorial control.

A second common narrative associates irregularity with criminality and disorder. In Italy, Garofalo (2025) highlights how political and media discourse often link irregular migrants to criminal economies, including drug trafficking and street crime, reinforcing perceptions of irregularity as a threat to social order. Similar framings appear in the UK, where Piemontese (2025) documents the discursive construction of irregularity as both a moral and security problem, often tied to images of “illegals” abusing welfare or involved in underground labour markets. These narratives extend the reach of irregularisation by conflating irregular status with moral undesirability.

At the same time, national contexts reveal important variations in counter-narratives. In the Netherlands and Poland, Hajer (2024) and Grzymała-Kazłowska and Homel-Ficenes (2025) show how civil society organisations have sought to reframe irregular migrants as vulnerable people in need of protection and rights, contrasting with the state's exclusionary discourse. In Germany, Rheindorf and Vollmer (2025) note humanitarian counterframes that emphasise dignity, children's rights, and moral obligations toward those who cannot be removed. Finland offers a different picture: Merikoski (2025) finds that irregular migration is relatively absent from public debate, but when it surfaces it is framed predominantly through asylum and humanitarian logics, indicating a narrow discursive repertoire.

At the EU level, Colombi (2025) demonstrates how irregularity is narrated within and across institutions of the European Commission. Competing discourses circulate: DG HOME prioritises security and returns; DG JUST and DG EMPL sometimes foreground rights, inclusion, and labour needs.

These contradictions show the Commission itself as an assemblage of competing agendas, whose interaction often reproduces restrictive framings but can also open spaces for contestation.

The assemblage perspective highlights how these narratives travel and interact across scales. Dominant tropes—border crossings, criminality, failed asylum—are not confined to national contexts but circulate transnationally through media, policy networks, and EU debates. At the same time, counter-discourses emerge from municipalities, NGOs, and transnational advocacy groups, pointing to the contested nature of irregularity as a discursive field.

Public perceptions

Surveys across six European countries confirm that public perceptions mirror and reinforce these dominant narratives while also exhibiting ambivalence. A common feature is the systematic overestimation of numbers. In Italy, respondents estimated irregular migrants to be more than half of all foreigners, compared to MIRREM estimates of under 10% (Garofalo, 2025). In Germany, the average estimate was 35.9% compared to 8–9% (Rheindorf & Vollmer, 2025). In Finland, respondents placed irregular migrants at over 30% of the foreign-born population, while MIRREM estimates are close to 1% (Merikoski, 2025). Such inflated estimates amplify the perception of irregular migration as a mass phenomenon, regardless of statistical evidence.

When asked about scenarios leading to irregularity, respondents across countries overwhelmingly identified border crossings and failed asylum claims. Other routes—visa overstays, expired work permits, children born into irregularity—were much less visible, despite their centrality in producing irregularity in practice (Näre et al., 2024). This mirrors the dominance of asylum and border narratives in political and media discourse, showing the circulation of these tropes into public opinion.

Patterns of social distance are also consistent. Respondents are most uncomfortable with irregular migrants working in intimate or proximate settings—such as their homes or workplaces—compared to encountering them in shops or restaurants. This was evident in Finland (Merikoski, 2025), Germany (Rheindorf & Vollmer, 2025), Italy (Garofalo, 2025), the Netherlands (Hajer, 2024), Poland (Grzymała-Każłowska & Homel-Ficenes, 2025), and the UK (Lessard-Phillips & Sigona, 2025). Such findings underline how irregularity is experienced not only as an abstract concern but as a relational issue tied to proximity and trust.

Respondents also consistently linked irregular migrants to specific work sectors. For men, construction, agriculture, and food delivery were most frequently mentioned; for women, cleaning and care work. Prostitution or sex work was also often mentioned spontaneously in free-text responses. These associations map closely onto labour market niches where precarious, unregulated work is concentrated, showing how perceptions intersect with infrastructures of irregularised labour.

On deservingness, experiments show ambivalent attitudes. Across countries, respondents were more supportive of measures linked to regularisation or granting citizenship to children than of extending access to general services. This conditional support suggests that irregular migrants are perceived as more deserving if linked to family, children, or gendered vulnerability.

Hiring choice experiments further illustrate the hierarchies of belonging embedded in perceptions. In nearly all countries, candidates of Ukrainian or other Eastern European origin were preferred over those from Africa, the Middle East, or South Asia. Length of residence, family presence in the host country, and personal recommendations all increased employability. Conversely, lack of language fluency strongly undermined perceptions of integration. These findings demonstrate how perceptions of irregular migrants are racialised, gendered, and conditioned by markers of social proximity.

The UK case provides an illustrative example (Lessard-Phillips & Sigona, 2025). Like elsewhere, concern about irregular migration is widespread (69.4%) and estimates are inflated (33.6% compared to 7.5%). Irregular migrants are strongly associated with food delivery, construction, cleaning, and catering, mirroring European patterns. Free-text responses frequently linked irregularity to criminality, echoing Italy's discursive nexus between irregular status and deviance. Hiring experiments revealed clear hierarchies: Moldovan candidates were more likely to be selected than those from Nigeria or Bangladesh, with women's employability more dependent on family presence and recommendations. Evaluations of integration were deeply racialised: Nigerians were judged less integrated than Kosovars, even when other attributes were held constant. Fluency in English and family networks in the UK improved perceptions, while their absence reinforced exclusion.

Taken together, narratives and perceptions constitute a powerful dimension of the irregularity assemblage. Political and media discourses set the terms through which irregularity is publicly imagined, while public perceptions both reproduce and reshape these narratives in everyday judgements about work, belonging, and integration. Both dimensions tend to narrow irregularity to a limited set of frames—border crossings, asylum, criminality—obscuring systemic processes of irregularisation such as visa dependency, bureaucratic failure, or labour market demand.

Yet both narratives and perceptions also reveal spaces of ambivalence and contestation. Public support for regularisation and citizenship for children, humanitarian counterframes advanced by NGOs and municipalities, and pragmatic recognition of migrants' labour contributions indicate that irregularity is not discursively fixed. Assemblage thinking allows us to see these contradictions not as noise but as potential openings for contingent alliances and shifts in governance.

Narratives and perceptions form a constitutive layer of the irregularity assemblage. They interact with infrastructures (Section 4.1) to legitimise precarisation and shape the everyday encounters that migrants experience (Section 4.3). They also structure the horizons of political possibility, narrowing what is thinkable but also offering counterframes and solidarities. By approaching them as assemblages, we can grasp not only their power in sustaining irregularity but also their instability, plurality, and potential for reconfiguration.

Lived Experiences of the Irregular Condition

The lived experiences of irregularised migrants make visible the embodied and situated character of irregularity. They reveal how specific configurations of infrastructures, discourses, and labour market regimes intersect in everyday life, producing irregularity not as an abstract legal status but as a set of vulnerabilities, dependencies, and strategies. The sectoral ethnographies conducted by I-CLAIM (WP5) show that irregularity is not only nationally configured but also sectorally assembled, with agriculture, food delivery, and domestic/care work generating distinct yet interconnected patterns of precarity. These findings also highlight the importance of an intersectional lens: race, gender, and class strongly shape how irregularity is experienced, who is most exposed, and what strategies are available to endure or resist.

Agriculture: cyclical irregularity and gendered vulnerability

Agriculture across Europe depends structurally on migrant labour, much of it precarious, irregularised and seasonal. Two features stand out.

First, irregularity is produced cyclically through temporary admission and selective regularisation timed with seasonal cycle. In Italy, women and men are recruited through seasonal permits but often

fall into irregularity when contracts end, or when amnesties (*sanatorie*) expire without opening longer-term prospects (Palumbo, 2025). In Poland Ukrainian workers on temporary protection perform undeclared work or enter on temporary schemes that provide labour flexibility but leave them vulnerable to abrupt irregularisation when employment relationships collapse or paperwork lapses (Matuszczyk, 2025). In Finland, restrictive documentary requirements for agricultural permits create barriers that drive workers into informality (Merikoski & Näre, 2025). Germany, despite more formal recruitment, also demonstrates how lapses in contracts or wage manipulation push workers into irregularity (Salamena, 2025).

Second, agricultural irregularity is gendered. In Italy, women are concentrated in feminised tasks (sorting, packaging) and face harassment and violence, with irregularity amplifying their vulnerability (Palumbo, 2025). In other contexts, men are given more advanced tasks (the operation of machines) and are better paid, while women often occupy less visible, less regulated roles, making them more exposed to informal arrangements and abuse. Gender intersects with race and class: African and South Asian workers are disproportionately confined to the hardest, least remunerated jobs, while Eastern European migrants are sometimes granted slightly more favourable conditions.

Commonalities across cases include the structural dependence on migrant labour, reliance on temporary permits, and normalisation of irregularity as part of agricultural production, producing a disposable workforce whose legality is contingent and cyclical.

Food delivery: digital infrastructures and racialised surveillance

Food delivery has become a crucial urban site where irregularity is lived and assembled. The reports identify two key dynamics.

First, irregular migrants enter delivery work through account rental and intermediated access. In the UK, irregularised riders often rent accounts from legal residents or intermediaries, paying high fees or surrendering a share of earnings (Sigona, Piemontese, Achi & Mendes, 2025), in Poland, the unregulated nature of the platform sector create a space for fleet partners, firms that play intermediary role between delivery platform and couriers (Homel & Grzymała-Kazłowska, 2025). This arrangement produces dependency and exposes migrants to exploitation: intermediaries can withhold pay or report workers to authorities. Riders are thus doubly precarious—lacking formal protection and dependent on private actors outside state oversight.

Second, irregularity is mediated by digital infrastructures and racialised enforcement. In the Netherlands, irregularised riders are under constant algorithmic monitoring, with risk of sudden deactivation (van Liempt & Hajer, 2025). In Berlin, irregular workers describe how enforcement raids intersect with narratives of fraud, producing a climate of racialised suspicion (Salamena, 2025). In the UK, media and political narratives frame account sharing as organised criminality, reinforcing migrants' precarious status and legitimising raids (Sigona et al., 2025). Gender is also significant: delivery is heavily masculinised, with women largely absent or invisible, reflecting the sector's physical demands and public visibility.

Commonalities include dependence on intermediated access to platforms, heightened precarity through algorithmic control, and enforcement strategies that criminalise irregular migrants. Differences lie in the degree of tolerance and enforcement: in the Netherlands, some municipalities turn a blind eye, while in the UK targeted raids make delivery workers a visible site of immigration control. Across all contexts, racial hierarchies are evident: African, South Asian, and Middle Eastern

migrants are more likely to be framed as fraudulent or criminal, while Eastern Europeans sometimes face less suspicion.

Domestic and care work: intimate labour, racialised and gendered

Domestic and care work shows how irregularity is produced in the most intimate of spaces. Three dynamics are prominent.

First, irregularity is generated by tied visas and employer dependence. In the UK, migrants recruited under care sponsorship visas risk irregularity if they leave exploitative employers; those who overstay visas or work outside sponsorship arrangements fall into irregularised limbo (Sigona, Piemontese, Mendes & Achi, 2025). Across Europe, dependency on employers for both income and legal status entrenches power asymmetries.

Second, irregularity in domestic work is structured by racialised and gendered hierarchies. In Italy, women from Eastern Europe and the Global South dominate the sector, with irregularity compounding their exposure to exploitation and exclusion (Marchetti & Lashchuk, 2025). In Finland, women in cleaning face precarious contracts and informal arrangements, with race shaping who is relegated to the most insecure jobs (Merikoski & Näre, 2025). In the Netherlands, irregularised migrants provide essential cleaning and childcare services, yet their work is systematically excluded from labour protections (Hajer & van Liempt, 2025).

Third, the private sphere amplifies invisibility and vulnerability. Exploitation—underpayment, excessive hours, harassment—occurs behind closed doors, shielded from regulation. Yet the same intimacy sometimes enables solidarity and protection, as when employers provide shelter or assistance to irregularised workers.

Commonalities include exclusion from formal protections, reliance on informality, and intersectional stratification along gendered and racial lines. Differences lie in national policy frameworks: Italy's structural informality and periodic amnesties; the UK's tied visa system; the Netherlands' reliance on NGOs and municipalities to fill protection gaps.

Situated and intersectional irregularity

The sectoral ethnographies make clear that irregularity is not lived in abstract legal terms but in embodied and situated forms of precarity. In agriculture, irregularity is cyclical and gendered, reflecting seasonal dependence and structural exclusion. In food delivery, it is mediated by digital infrastructures and racialised enforcement, intertwining legal precarity with algorithmic control. In domestic and care work, it is embedded in intimate, gendered, and racialised relations of labour and dependency.

Across these sectors, irregularity is consistently produced by governance strategies that design precarity into migration and labour systems. Yet the assemblage perspective shows how irregularity is also differentiated: sectoral logics, racialised hierarchies, and gendered divisions produce uneven experiences and vulnerabilities. Migrants are not passive: they develop strategies to endure—renting accounts, switching employers, relying on community networks—but these often deepen dependency rather than resolve it.

By connecting infrastructures (Section 4.1), narratives and perceptions (Section 4.2), and lived experiences (this section), we see irregularity as a multi-scalar and intersectional assemblage: structured from above, refracted through discourses, and embodied in everyday work and life. This perspective makes visible not only the vulnerabilities of irregularised migrants but also the

contradictions, tensions, and potential solidarities through which the irregular condition is continually negotiated.

Conclusion: Advancing the Research Agenda on Irregularity

This paper has argued that irregularity should be approached as an assemblage: a contingent constellation of legal frameworks, infrastructures, discourses, and everyday practices that, together, shape migrants' conditions of life. From this perspective, irregularity is not reducible to legal status alone, nor simply the outcome of policy failure. It is actively produced and sustained through governance strategies, bureaucratic practices, market logics, and narratives of belonging and exclusion.

What migrants experience in concrete terms—the irregular condition—is the lived consequence of these configurations. It encompasses chronic insecurity, constrained mobility, and dependence on informal arrangements, but also forms of endurance, solidarity, and strategic adaptation. The irregular condition is always situated, taking different shape in the agricultural fields of Southern Europe, in the homes of Northern European cities, or on the streets where riders navigate platform economies. It is also intersectional: gender, race, age, and class mediate who is channelled into specific forms of precarious labour, who is tolerated, and who is criminalised. Furthermore, the irregular condition has intergenerational ramifications—affecting children born into irregularity or growing up in households with precarious status—and transnational consequences, as migrants' legal precarity reverberates across borders through remittances, family separations, and onward mobility.

This conceptualisation has several implications for future research. First, much of the literature continues to focus on migrants at a single point in time, often framed through entry, settlement, or return. Yet I-CLAIM and other studies show that irregularity is often cyclical and patterned by design. Migrants move in and out of status, shift between formal and informal labour, and endure periods of toleration punctuated by the threat of removal. Longitudinal research is needed to trace how these trajectories unfold across the life course and across generations, and to capture the cumulative impact of protracted insecurity on health, education, family life, and ageing.

Second, research remains heavily concentrated in Europe and North America, even though irregular migration is central to regimes in the Gulf, Asia, Africa, and Latin America. Hannoum (2019), for example, illustrates how the frameworks to discuss European and African migration are completely separated. Applying the assemblage approach beyond the West would expand the empirical base, reveal new logics of irregularisation, and avoid reifying Eurocentric models. Samaddar (2020) for example writes how the Northern gaze on migration disguises, displaces and reconfigures realities of migration. Comparative work should also pay attention to multi-scalar processes: how EU-level directives intersect with national frameworks, and how municipal practices shape everyday realities.

Third, the irregular condition is not experienced evenly and the production of it is tied to modern conceptualisation of citizenship and its racialised exclusionary principles (Bhambra 2015). Women in domestic and care work confront vulnerabilities tied to the sexualisation of racialised bodies; men in food delivery face algorithmic surveillance and public policing; racialised hierarchies structure who is considered “deserving” of protection and who is rendered disposable. Future research should foreground these differentiated experiences and situate them within broader structures of gendered and racialised labour markets. Intergenerational analysis is also critical, as children inherit or resist their parents' precarious status in ways that shape belonging and citizenship claims.

Fourth, assemblage thinking includes the human as well as the non-human and draws attention to the infrastructures through which irregularity is mediated—not only legal and policy frameworks, but also recruitment systems, digital platforms, welfare bureaucracies, and even payment apps or housing markets. These infrastructures are not neutral backdrops but active producers of irregularity, enabling both surveillance and survival. Research must continue to explore how infrastructures intersect with enforcement and with migrants’ strategies of endurance.

Finally, the irregularity assemblage is not only a structure of domination but also a terrain of negotiation. Civil society organisations, trade unions, local authorities, and even certain EU directorates create openings for new alliances that may mitigate or challenge the irregular condition. Studying these sites can help identify how migrants’ rights are defended in practice, how solidarities are built across diverse actors, and under what conditions precarisation can be resisted or reversed.

In advancing this agenda, researchers should also remain reflexive about their own role. Research practices themselves are part of the assemblage, shaping how irregularity is defined, who is represented, and which voices are amplified. Treating scholarship as a “research assemblage” underscores the importance of methodological pluralism and ethical attentiveness, while recognising the situated nature of knowledge production.

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